

***Moringa Oleifera* as a Green Nano Factory of Silver Nanoparticles**

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Abstract

For the green production of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), *Moringa oleifera* offers a wealth of natural reducing and stabilizing agents, providing an eco-friendly substitute for chemical processes. This review highlights the plant's phytochemical role in AgNP formation, compares its efficiency with other biological and chemical approaches, and summarizes essential characterization techniques. Moringa-derived AgNPs demonstrate strong antimicrobial, anticancer, environmental, and agricultural potential. Key challenges include variability in plant metabolites, lack of standardized protocols, and limited toxicity data. Addressing these gaps will support scalable and safe applications.

Keywords

Green Synthesis, Phytochemicals, Silver Nanoparticles, Sustainable Nanotechnology.

Introduction

Nanoscience enables the design of materials with enhanced properties at the 1–100 nm scale [1][2]. Conventional methods for producing metallic nanoparticles are increasingly restricted due to toxic chemicals, high energy requirements, and expensive post-processing [3][4]. These limitations have driven the adoption of green synthesis - an economical and environmentally beneficial biological method, now widely used for producing silver nanoparticles [5][6]. *Moringa oleifera*, a fast-growing plant rich in nutrients and diverse phytochemicals [7], provides an excellent natural source for stabilizing and reducing agents in creation of nanoparticles. Considering its phytochemical abundance, this work utilizes *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract for the sustainable production of silver nanoparticles, anticipating improved stability and antimicrobial performance [8].

Objective of study

This review highlights the plant's phytochemical role in AgNP formation, compares its efficiency with other biological and chemical approaches, and summarizes essential characterization techniques.

Review of Literature

This is the review based paper so latest reviews are discussed through out the paper.

Analysis

Overview of *Moringa oleifera* – Phytochemistry and relevance to Nanoparticles Synthesis

A number of substances found in *Moringa oleifera's* leaves, seeds, and bark contribute to the plant's phytochemistry, which supports its function as an agent that stabilises and reduces the production of AgNPs.

Fig 1: Key phytochemical components in *Moringa oleifera*

1. **Flavonoids:** Quercetin and kaempferol act as strong electron donors that reduce Ag⁺ to AgNPs and cap the particles through their aromatic structures, enhancing stability [9].
2. **Phenolic compounds:** Phenolics such as caffeine and chlorogenic acid reduce silver ions via their antioxidant activity and reactive hydroxyl groups, supporting AgNP formation [10].
3. **Tannins:** Tannins efficiently donate electrons for Ag⁺ reduction and simultaneously cap AgNPs, preventing aggregation and improving stability [11].
4. **Saponins:** Saponins act as natural surfactants that aid Ag⁺ reduction through glycosidic groups and stabilize AgNPs by preventing aggregation [11].

Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles

Fig 2: Process of synthesizing AgNPs

Fresh *Moringa oleifera* leaves are washed, dried, powdered, and extracted by heating 5 g powder in 100 mL of deionised water at 90°C for 1 hour, followed by filtration [12].

Mixing 2.5 mL extract with 1 mM AgNO₃ produces a light-brown solution that turns dark brown overnight, confirming Ag⁺ reduction and AgNP formation [13].

AgNPs are isolated by centrifugations at 10,000 rpm for 10 min, followed by a wash with DI water and an overnight drying at 55 °C [14].

Comparative Study: Relevance of *M. oleifera* for Eco-friendly Silver Nanoparticles Production
Table 1: Comparison of different aspects

Aspect	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Leaf Extract	Other Plant Extracts	Chemical Synthesis	Ref
Phytochemicals	Rich in flavonoids, phenolics, proteins, strong reducing & capping agents	Lower or variable phytochemical content	Uses toxic chemical reducers	[15] [16]
Reduction Efficiency	Strong antioxidants reduce Ag ⁺ efficiently	Variable reducing ability	Requires high energy; produces toxic by-products	[17] [18]
Stabilization	Proteins/tannins prevent aggregation; stable AgNPs	Often weaker stabilization	Needs synthetic, toxic stabilizers	[19] [15]
Eco-friendliness	Fully green and non-toxic	Green but sometimes less sustainable	Generates hazardous waste	[16]
Cost	Low-cost, widely available	May be costly or less accessible	High cost due to chemicals & waste management	[20]
Biocompatibility	Highly biocompatible	Varies by plant	Often low; potential toxicity	[18]

Characterization and analysis of Silver Nanoparticles

UV-Visible Spectroscopy: AgNPs are frequently verified using UV-visible spectroscopy through a characteristic SPR peak within 200–800 nm, corresponding to particles in the 2–100 nm range [21-23]. The SPR band varies with particle size and medium, and its long-term retention in biogenic AgNPs indicates high stability [24].

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM): TEM provides precise information on nanoparticle size, shape, and crystallinity [25-27]. Based on electron transmission, it enables high-resolution imaging and offers a resolution roughly 1,000 times greater than SEM [26][28].

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR): FTIR identifies functional groups and surface biomolecules involved in nanoparticle stabilization and reduction [25] [29]. By measuring infrared absorption patterns, FTIR serves as an easy, non-destructive, and affordable way to verify that biological substances play a part in AgNP production [28][30].

X-Ray Diffraction Spectroscopy (XRD): XRD is essential for determining crystalline structure and phase composition. The angles and intensities of diffracted X-rays provide insight into the material’s crystal phases and structural properties [31]. While XRF identifies elemental composition, XRD remains key for confirming AgNP crystallinity.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): SEM is commonly used to analyse the size and surface morphology of AgNP [32]. It detects secondary electrons emitted from the sample surface, enabling detailed visualization of 3D structural features.

Applications of Silver Nanoparticles

Figure 3: Silver NPs applications

Antimicrobial Activity

AgNPs derived from *Moringa* exhibit strong antimicrobial effects, effectively inhibiting microbes like *E. Coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* [33-34][17]. Their activity results from membrane disruption and oxidative stress, enhanced by phytochemical capping layers rich in flavonoids and phenolics [34,35]. Notably, they also act against resistant strains like MRSA while maintaining low cytotoxicity at moderate doses [17][36].

Anticancer Activity

Biogenic AgNPs from *M. oleifera* demonstrate selective cytotoxicity, reducing the viability of breast (MCF-7) and colon cancerous cells with minimal impact on healthy cells [37]. The anticancer action involves ROS generation, DNA damage, and apoptosis, with synergistic effects reported in oral cancer models [38]. Green synthesis further supports their therapeutic applicability [17].

Drug Delivery

Moringa-stabilized AgNPs serve as biocompatible carriers capable of controlled drug loading and release [36]. Functionalized nanogels derived from Moringa gum enable pH-responsive delivery of agents like doxorubicin, supporting targeted therapeutic applications [39][40].

Environmental Remediation

Moringa-based AgNPs effectively adsorb heavy metals, including Hg(II) [43], and catalyze sunlight-driven degradation of dyes and pharmaceutical residues through ROS formation [19][42]. Their green, low-cost synthesis makes them suitable for sustainable wastewater treatment [19][41-43].

Agricultural Applications

These AgNPs act as biostimulants, improving growth and stress tolerance in crops. Benefits include enhanced yield in drought-stressed *Pelargonium hortorum* [44], improved resilience in tomato [45], and increased growth and carotene content in maize [46], supporting their use as eco-friendly nano fertilizers.

Table 2: Challenges, Limitations, and Standardization Issues

Category	Issue	Description	Ref.
Challenges	Variation in plant metabolites	Phytochemical differences across plant parts and seasons lead to inconsistent nanoparticle properties.	[16] [47]
	Sensitivity to conditions of the reaction	The extract-precursor ratio, temperature, and pH all affect the results of synthesis.	[48]
	Scale-up limitations	Large-batch production is affected by extract instability and uneven yield.	[49]
Limitations	Stability concerns	Green-synthesized AgNPs may aggregate or oxidize during storage.	[16]
	Insufficient toxicity data	Limited long-term and in vivo toxicological evidence is available.	[37]
	Narrow characterization	Many studies lack detailed surface chemistry and stability parameters.	[47] [49]
Standardisation Issues	No unified synthesis protocol	Extraction and reaction steps vary widely between studies.	[48]
	Inconsistent reporting	Key physicochemical parameters are not uniformly documented.	[49]

Future Prospects and Research Directions

Table 3: Future Prospects & Research Directions

Application Area	Future Prospect	Ref.
Antileishmanial therapy	Nanomedicine for cutaneous leishmaniasis enhances antioxidant defense	[50]
Antimicrobial / Antibiofilm Agents	Antimicrobial coatings, wound dressings, and disinfectants against resistant strains	[17]
Anticancer(general)	Targeted chemo/immunotherapy; effective against colon cancer, leukemia, melanoma	[51]
Optical Devices	Optical limiters and photonic devices with nonlinear optical properties	[52]
Environmental Remediation	Water purification and pollutant degradation using eco-friendly AgNPs	[53] [54]
Women's Hygiene	Feminine hygiene products with antimicrobial action against <i>S. aureus</i> and <i>C. albicans</i>	[55] [56]
Multifunctional Biomedical Formulations	Combating infection, oxidative stress, and thrombosis with multifunctional AgNPs	[57] [58]
Medical Packaging and Surface Coatings	Composite MO-AgNP-ZnO nanoparticles for antimicrobial films and clinical surfaces	[59] [60]

Conclusion

An environmentally benign and sustainable substitute for traditional chemical procedures is the manufacture of silver nanoparticles using green nanotechnology. Moringa's phytochemicals effectively reduce and stabilize Ag⁺ ions, producing stable, crystalline nanoparticles with confirmed antimicrobial and antioxidant potential. While these findings highlight broad applications in

healthcare, agriculture, and environment, challenges such as process variability, standardization, and safety assessment remain. Addressing these gaps through optimized protocols, mechanistic studies, and regulatory evaluation will be essential for scalable and responsible use. Overall, Moringa-mediated silver nanoparticles present a promising pathway toward greener nanotechnology

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